

Abstract

This study explores the performance of Quantum Support Vector Classifiers (QSVCs) and Quantum Neural Networks (QNNs) in comparison to classical models for machine learning tasks. By evaluating these models on the Iris and MNIST-PCA datasets, we find that quantum models tend to outperform classical approaches as the problem complexity increases. While QSVCs generally provide more consistent results, QNNs exhibit superior performance in higher-complexity tasks due to their increased quantum load. Additionally, we analyze the impact of hyperparameter tuning, showing that feature maps and ansatz configurations significantly influence model accuracy. We also compare the PennyLane and Qiskit frameworks, concluding that Qiskit provides better optimization and efficiency for our implementation. These findings highlight the potential of Quantum Machine Learning (QML) for complex classification problems and provide insights into model selection and optimization strategies.

Introduction

- Motivation**
 - Classical machine learning models are successful but face challenges with high-dimensional and complex data.
 - Quantum Machine Learning (QML) seeks to leverage quantum principles—superposition, interference, and entanglement—to enhance model performance and efficiency.
- Focus of the study**
 - Compare the performance of **Quantum Support Vector Classifiers (QSVCs)** and **Quantum Neural Networks (QNNs)**.
 - Use different datasets and different Feature Maps and Ansatzes.
- Research goals**
 - Assess whether quantum models provide a performance advantage as problem complexity increases.
 - Compare QSVCs and QNNs in terms of accuracy, consistency, and hyperparameter sensitivity.
 - Investigate the role of quantum feature maps and ansätze configurations.
 - Evaluate and compare Qiskit and PennyLane frameworks for implementation efficiency.

Datasets

- Iris Dataset**
 - Classic ML benchmark with 3 classes and 4 features.
 - Used to verify if quantum models can handle basic classification.
 - Expected: classical models perform better due to simplicity.
- MNIST-PCA Dataset**
 - Binary classification of digits 3 vs 5 from MNIST, reduced via PCA to 2-20 features.
 - Used to simulate more complex, real-world tasks.
 - Expected: quantum models closer in performance to classical ones due to higher complexity.

Feature Maps and Ansatzes

- Feature Maps**
 - A Feature Map is a quantum circuit that encodes classical input data into a quantum state in a high-dimensional Hilbert space, enabling quantum models to process and distinguish patterns in the data.
 - The choice of feature map affects how well a quantum model can separate different classes.
 - Feature maps can be non-entangling (e.g., ZFeatureMap in Figure 1) or include entanglement (e.g., ZZFeatureMap) to capture more complex correlations.
- Ansätze**
 - An ansatz is a parameterized quantum circuit used to model trainable functions, where its gate parameters are optimized during training to solve a specific task such as classification or regression.
 - They are comprised of Rotation gates (e.g., Ry, Rz) for learnable parameters and entangling gates (e.g., CNOT) to create correlations between qubits.
 - Common ansatz designs include: RealAmplitudes (real-valued rotations + entanglement) or EfficientSU2 (uses SU(2)-based rotations (Y and Z) with entanglement, see Figure 2).

Figure 1. Visualization of a ZFeatureMap circuit with 2 repetitions and 3 features

Figure 2. Visualization of an efficient SU2 circuit with 1 repetition and 3 features

Quantum Machine Learning Models

- Quantum Support Vector Machines (QSVCs)**
 - Extend classical SVMs by using quantum kernels.
 - Quantum kernel: Computes inner products in high-dimensional quantum Hilbert space via a quantum feature map.
 - Approaches used:
 - Regular Quantum Kernel Estimation: Uses the Compute–Uncompute method to build a kernel matrix for a classical SVM.
 - Trainable Quantum Kernel: Augments the feature map (e.g., ZZFeatureMap) with additional parameterized gates (e.g., Ry gates). Parameters are optimized (e.g., with SPSA) to improve kernel performance.
- Quantum Neural Networks (QNNs) using Variational Quantum Circuits (VQCs)**
 - VQCs are near-term hybrid quantum-classical models.
 - Their architecture includes: Feature Map (Encodes classical data into quantum states), Ansatz (Trainable parameterized quantum circuit with rotation and entanglement gates), Measurement Layer (Measures quantum state to obtain output), Cost Function (Cross-entropy loss to guide training), Optimizer (Classical methods like SPSA used to minimize loss).

Iris Classification Experiment

- Execution: 80/20 split, with 500 repetitions per model for statistical reliability.
- Results are shown in Table 1 for the classical models: Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and Support Vector Classifier (SVC); and for the quantum models: Quantum Support Vector Classifier (QSVC), QSVC with trained kernel (QSVCTK) and Variational Quantum Classifier (VQC).
- Key Insights**
 - VQC showed the lowest performance, likely due to greater circuit complexity and training difficulty.
 - QSVC closely matched classical SVC, indicating strong potential for quantum kernel methods.

	Classical vs Quantum				
	Classical models		Quantum models		
Model	ANN	SVC	QSVC	QSVCTK	VQC
Accuracy	0.9521	0.9598	0.9589	0.9546	0.9233
Failure Rate	0.0479	0.0402	0.0411	0.0454	0.0767
Sensitivity (Recall)	0.9534	0.9612	0.9608	0.9561	0.9317
Specificity	0.9765	0.9807	0.9802	0.9780	0.9638
PPV	0.9572	0.9630	0.9622	0.9584	0.9331
NPV	0.9777	0.9811	0.9804	0.9785	0.9652
F1-Score	0.9494	0.9572	0.9568	0.9521	0.9200

Table 1. Macro Average Metrics for the best hyperparameters combination of each model for the Iris classification

MNIST-PCA Classification Experiment

- Execution: 85/15 train/test split with balanced classes. Results are shown in Table 2.
- Each model was run only once per configuration due to longer training times (higher complexity).
- Key Insights**
 - Quantum models outperformed classical models in this more complex task.
 - VQC was the best performer overall, reversing its lower performance from the Iris task.
 - Indicates that quantum advantage increases with problem complexity.
 - QNNs benefit significantly from deeper (more repeated) ansätze.

	Classical vs Quantum				
	Classical models		Quantum models		
Model	ANN	SVC	QSVC	QSVCTK	VQC
Accuracy	0.9099	0.9132	0.9264	0.9227	0.9338
Failure Rate	0.0901	0.0868	0.0736	0.0773	0.0662
Sensitivity (Recall)	0.9829	0.9837	0.9832	0.9776	0.9518
Specificity	0.8455	0.8510	0.8762	0.8743	0.9178
PPV	0.8493	0.8546	0.8752	0.8729	0.9109
NPV	0.9825	0.9835	0.9833	0.9779	0.9557
F1-Score	0.9111	0.9144	0.9261	0.9223	0.9309

Table 2. Macro Average Metrics for the best hyperparameters combination of each model for the MNIST-PCA class.

Conclusions

- Quantum models outperform classical ones as task complexity increases (notably on MNIST-PCA).
- QSVCs are more stable and effective on simple problems; VQCs scale better and excel on complex tasks.
- Increasing quantum depth (quantum load) improves model performance.
- ZFeatureMap outperforms ZZFeatureMap; optimal performance requires careful tuning of repetitions (in general, performance improves with more repetitions).
- Qiskit is the preferred framework for speed and hardware integration; PennyLane better suits AI framework compatibility.
- Future work: larger datasets, new ansätze, hybrid models, and real quantum hardware testing.

References

- Diego Alvarez-Estevéz. Benchmarking quantum machine learning kernel training for classification tasks. *IEEE Transactions on Quantum Engineering*, 6:1–15, 2025.
- Vojtěch Havlíček, Antonio D Córcoles, Kristan Temme, Aram W Harrow, Abhinav Kandala, Jerry M Chow, and Jay M Gambetta. Supervised learning with quantum-enhanced feature spaces. *Nature*, 567(7747):209–212, 2019.
- Keisuke Mitarai, Makoto Negoro, Masahiro Kitagawa, and Keisuke Fujii. Quantum circuit learning. *Physical Review A*, 98(3):032309, 2018.

Acknowledgements

This work has been supported by the State Research Agency of the Spanish Government under Project PID2023-147422OB-I00 funded by MCIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by the Xunta de Galicia (Grant ED431C 2022/44), both supported by the EU European Regional Development Fund (ERDF). DAE has also received support from project RYC2022-038121-I, funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and European Social Fund Plus (ESF+).

CITIC, as a center accredited for excellence within the Galician University System and a member of the CIGUS Network, receives subsidies from the Department of Education, Science, Universities, and Vocational Training of the Xunta de Galicia. Additionally, it is co-financed by the EU through the FEDER Galicia 2021-27 operational program (Ref. ED431G 2023/01).